

NFDI4Ing's success story 2021

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Introduction

NFDI4Ing is a consortium from the first round of applications of Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI). NFDI4Ing's goal is to make the

data accruing throughout the entire engineering research process sustainably accessible, which means in a citable form according to [FAIR](#) principles and under licenses that are as free as possible. The funding programme has started as of October 1st 2020, and after the initial kick-off, our Task Areas (TAs) now look back on their accomplishments from 2021. For détails regarding the work programme, please refer to our [published proposal](#).

Archetypes

ALEX – bespoke experiments with high variability of setups

2021 was a successful year for TA ALEX. Despite the pandemic, we regularly met at project and work meetings and discussed the development of the TA ALEX aims. Moreover, we actively participated in events and conferences, such as the NFDI4ing Conference or the Community Meeting *Construction Engineering and Architecture* (DFG 45) to disseminate our work. In the following, we list some of the activities that were presented at these events.

At the Chair of Fluid Systems, the development of the tool PlotID was kickstarted as a first step towards FAIR plots and diagrams. PlotID works in two steps: In the first step the plot is labelled with an ID and in a second step the research data is packed. With the ID, you can reconnect and share the specific data of this diagram. Within Task A-2-4 of our Measure *modular approach to reusable bespoke solutions*, a concept has been developed for creating a machine-readable characteristic and impact sheet (CIS). As an alternative to conventional data sheets, CIS use controlled vocabularies from industry standards and W3C standards for creating a semantic information model of components adapted to individual applications. The concept has been presented on a poster at

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the annual meeting of Process and Plant Engineering Community and a conference paper is under review at the 13th International Fluid Power Conference Aachen.

At the Institute for Reactive Flows and Diagnostics a new data center was built based on own internal funding. In addition to research data management (RDM)-compliant storage, backup and archiving of the institute's data, this data center also serves as a test bed and benchmark environment for a secure research data workflow and the possible as well as necessary technical boundary conditions. Using the application of a gas mixing system for characterization of gas sensors systems for indoor air quality monitoring, the Lab for Measurement Technology at University of Saarland is pursuing an automated integration of all information that are necessary for interpretation and long-term use of the experiment performed, into the metadata of the measurement file. At the Research Center Energy Storage Technologies of Clausthal University of Technology, experiments for battery tests were evaluated and electronic lab books were introduced.

We are looking forward to developing these activities further and starting new ones in 2022!

BETTY – engineering research software

In 2021, the task area BETTY has been focusing on three main topics related to research software: quality assurance, reproducibility and findability. Our vision is that the engineering sciences produce validated, high-quality software that can be found and reused by other researchers in their own research. To make research software findable, we have laid out the concept for a service that allows users to specifically search for research software repositories using domain-specific terms, as e.g. an

algorithm or a mathematical method. The service is anticipated to go live at some point in 2022.

Computational research often involves a series of different tasks, performed by different pieces of software that have to be executed in a particular order, passing the data produced by one task as input to a subsequent task. In order for research to be reproducible, it is beneficial if this process is automated and made publicly available. Therefore, we have initiated the Special Interest Group „Tools for describing, reproducing and reusing scientific workflows“, in which we are currently evaluating a number of workflow languages and tools regarding their usefulness to be employed in research, focusing on measures such as ease-of-use, composability, capabilities of encapsulating the required software environments and support for HPC (High-Performance-Computing) environments. The documentation of this project is provided in a public git repository ([link](#)).

Finally, we are thinking about means to facilitate quality assurance for researchers that write software. Our focus so far has been on research software that is used to carry out simulations of physical processes, which is a wide-spread use case in the engineering sciences. For such code bases, regression tests provide an easy means of testing the software by using small simulations as tests, comparing the results against reference solutions that were obtained beforehand. In order to help researchers to use this technique, we are currently developing a Python framework that provides the tools required to compare simulation results, and which supports a wide range of standard file formats. At the same time, we are developing a small C++ library that researchers can use in their code to write the simulation data obtained with their own methods and data structures into these standard file formats.

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CADEN – provenance tracking of physical samples & data samples

It has been an exiting year for CADEN: We've got to know our community better, and we finished the foundation for what we want to provide eventually. Although there is no polished end product yet, there are well-defined intermediate milestone achieved, and there is already something that you can give a try.

Our vision is to let electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) and other local databases of scientific output talk to each other. The year 2021 convinced us that this is a realistic goal, even though we depend on ELN developers to implement our protocol. With SciMesh, we gave the data exchange a framework, hopefully finding the sweet spot between flexibility and interoperability. This needs to become more concrete in 2022, and of course, be actually brought to life in ELN software. And with JuliaBase, we have a reference implementation that is able to export all of its data in a rich, highly structured knowledge graph.

However, the most unsuccessful aspect in CADEN in 2021 was the lack of community participation. It is vitally important that you, the scientist – the user of what we wish to create – get in touch with us! Visit SciMesh's website and send comments by email. We would be very happy to discuss SciMesh with some of you in an online meeting. And, in case you are an IT-savvy, install our ELN prototype and kick the tyres. You may submit everything you observe in GitHub issues, or share it with us in an online meeting.

DORIS – high performance measurement & computation

The high-performance measuring and computing (HPMC) group within NFDI4Ing had a prosper year and is eagerly working on all Measures. The

interdisciplinary and interinstitutional team is fully staffed and achieved first important milestones.

-Tool development: To naturally create ontology-conforming metadata fields accompanying research, DORIS recently released a metadata crawler. It allows automated extraction of metadata from simulations or experiments conducted on HPMC systems (crawler: gitlab.lrz.de/nfdi4ing/crawler). To get the most appropriate use of the automated metadata extraction, a HPMC-sub-ontology is developed in consultation with the special interest group "Metadata and Ontologies" as well as pilot users from the HPMC community.

Due to the high storage demands (hundreds of TB or even PB), HPMC data are currently immobile and too large to be copied to local work stations. Therefore, new concepts for data storage, findability, access and transfer have to be implemented and evaluated. As first test, a searchable and indexable local storage to front-end interface has been provided ([TUM Workbench](#) ↔ [LRZ DSS](#) storage). The storage is accessible through the local virtual research environment; an individual access management system can be implemented. To support the scientific community and to gain further improvement through testing and feedback, a users' guide has been published.

-Applications: The (post-) processing of archetypal research data generated in the HPMC community usually is executed on HPC systems. Individual and custom-tailored software solutions that can be transferred to other systems are developed and tested within DORIS. To evaluate the feasibility of containers/dockers for reproducibility on HPC systems, DORIS successfully issued several project applications at all [GCS](#) participants. Test runs on SuperMUC/LRZ and JUWELS/JSC have already been conducted. Due to current low performance and efficiency, DORIS will

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improve methods to develop and share best-practice recommendations for reproducibility of simulations on HPC systems.

-Obstacles: Common frames within project applications at HPC facilities don't consider RDM-projects, and some systems or software cannot be accessed by non-institutional users. These obstacles could be resolved through pilot users and project members at GCS facilities or associated institutions.

In general, a strong dependence on 3rd party service providers, their policies and infrastructure (computing centers, software development) can be seen as a major obstacle. As a consequence, networking and an inclusive, interinstitutional approach are inevitable means for success.

-Community outreach: The full benefit for the NFDI effort in the context of HPMC with very large data lies in the usage of previously inaccessible data through third-party research groups. To transfer the gained knowledge and outcome, and to promote the preexisting or newly developed tools, community-based training and workshops are provided by DORIS in coordination with special interest group "Basic RDM Training". First benefits could be shown to the community in a local (Munich based) workshop and will be consolidated in a nationwide workshop in [April 2022](#). DORIS contributed to several meetings and conferences and always tries to increase the acceptance of NFDI4Ing benefits by promoting the outcomes and supporting the scientific community. A user based requirement assessment workshop regarding protection of legitimate expectation ("Vertrauensschutz") for data has been held, and a generic template for a HPMC [data management plan](#) has been published.

To intrigue future scientists for RDM, and to enable them to apply their RDM skills within undergraduate studies, a new [module](#) on RDM in engineering sciences at TU Munich has been proposed and approved. The lecture will premiere in the summer semester 2022 with participation of internal and external lecturers and could modularly be expanded to other universities or research domains.

[ELLEN – extensive and heterogeneous data requirements](#)

In the first year of the Ellen Task Area, we succeeded in building a semantic framework that allows research software and datasets to be described in detail and linked together, in addition to traditional text publications. A link to the terminology service of the NFDI4Ing BASE SERVICES was established to support ontology-compliant metadata capture. The framework has been embedded in the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG), which now enables cross-data type searches for research content.

The more scientists describe their research output in the form of publications, software, and data on this platform, the greater the potential for recognizing and utilizing connections between previously independent artifacts becomes. For example, publications which analyze a certain data set or software combinations which can generate a specific type of data set can now be automatically recognized.

In the last year, the activities in Ellen established a close connection to the research area of Energy Systems Analysis (ESA). In particular, the added value of ontologies and metadata standards in the area of data management and search were addressed during various community events. Furthermore, the ESA domain was supported in its efforts to

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further develop its domain ontology "Open Energy Ontology (OEO)" and to embed it in current project activities.

FRANK – many participants & simultaneous devices

Task Area FRANK started 2021 rather slowly as the first tasks to be addressed were to clarify the state of the art regarding RDM amongst the TA FRANK Participants and Use Cases. Therefore several approaches were chosen, one of which was a survey regarding RDM and Tools used in this context. Furthermore, interviews took place to identify needs and wishes of researchers. By this, the requirements for the planned RDM-framework were gathered. This framework aims to be a decision-supporting tool with tips and tricks as well as references to further literature and trainings for RDM which escorts the researchers through their very own workflow.

On the 2021, NFDI4Ing Conference FRANK held a Workshop, which led to User Stories that further elaborate the structure of research as well as connections between researchers and their day-to-day surroundings. This was the next step in unravelling out the complex requirements such framework has to meet. The last step in the requirement analysis were Workflow-Workshops held with different Participants of the TA FRANK, to get a good glimpse of everyday challenges in the lives of different researchers. FRANK closed 2021 with a round-up of the collected requirements, a comparison between the archived and planned goals as well as a determination of the further development of the FRANK RDM Framework (working name).

2022 will come up with new challenges for FRANK, especially the implementation of the planned framework. Therefore, mayor decisions have to be made: Will the framework be a program or a guideline?

Should it be an online tool or some local instance? The tracks for those decisions are already laid out!

GOLO – field data & distributed systems

In GOLO, we look back on an exciting and successful year 2021. The three project partners from Leibniz University Hannover (LUH), the German Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI) and Technical University Dresden (TUD) worked together to develop basic principles for research data management of field data using the concept of the digital twin. With the typification and classification of data and information in field experiments and the implementation of a metadata concept for field data, we laid the foundation for the further development of the digital twin in research data management. To help scientists decide which data to record, store, and publish, we have developed a best practice for handling required and optional research data. Due to the boundary conditions in the field as well as sensor and system characteristics, field data have many characteristics. By identifying the essential characteristics, we can uniquely describe field data via metadata and assist researchers in selecting data analysis methods for their field data. The results will be published in 2022. In cooperation with the NFDI4Ing Base Service *quality assurance in RDM processes and metrics for FAIR data*, we implemented and evaluated a research data management organization plan (RDMO) for various research questions and projects.

At LUH, a research vehicle has been equipped with several sensors, e.g. cameras and LiDAR, which will be the basis for numerous of field tests starting in 2022. Furthermore, in the new year we will realize our thoughts and concepts on research data management with the digital twin based on our research objects in order to establish a uniform data interface between research and industry.

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BASE SERVICES

Research software development

-Technische Universität Darmstadt (TUDa): We started a knowledge base for the development of scientific software. We address the topics version control, continuous integration, test driven development and many more. We see it as a success that we did not only get an approved workflow from the collaborative research centre SFB1194 at TUDa but were (and still are) also able to refine our articles in cooperation with other activities. These include the Institute of hydraulic engineering at TUDa, as well as the TA BETTY and TA ALEX.

-University of Stuttgart: We set up a JupyterHub that allows scientists to interactively execute code and enrich the code with text, figures and more (literate programming). At the moment the JupyterHub is in testing mode and not available for everybody, but it will become productive in the next year. Nevertheless, we invite all interested scientists to become test users to make this service as beneficial as possible.

Metadata and terminology services

The past year has provided much momentum for our BASE SERVICES Measure *metadata and terminology services* and has resulted in a number of tangible and increasingly integrated deliverables. Specifically, the following goals and solutions were worked on:

-*Application Profiles* are a way to define application-specific interoperable metadata schemata by making use of existing semantic terms. By using them within a hierarchical and modular modelling approach, these profiles are highly flexible and can easily be reused and/or adapted. We have implemented a first software demonstrator that facilitates generating, sharing, finding and reusing these metadata profiles.

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-The *Terminology Service* builds a technical infrastructure for terminology management and access. We have implemented a web-based service (Minimal Viable Product) that enables access, curation, and subscription to domain specific metadata schemas (ontologies).

-The *Metadata Hub* supports Data Management of metadata documents. We have provided a first prototype (the repository turntable), that enables uniform access through a uniform application programming interface (API).

The individual services are designed to cooperate closely with each other. We have already been able to address this to a large extent. We also have a lively exchange with project partners outside our BASE SERVICES Measure *metadata and terminology services*. Among others, the Measure is in regular contact with various archetypes (GOLO, ELLEN, ALEX and FRANK) to discuss potential joint use cases and collaboration. We have organized and participated in various community events to make our solutions known (e.g. OntoCommons workshop, RDA Virtual Plenary 18, OEO-Steering Group workshop, and the NFDI Conference). In addition, we have raised awareness about our work in various social media (Twitter and blogs) and we have prepared a contribution to the upcoming NFDI4Ing newsletter.

Although we have been able to make good progress, it remains one of the big challenges to establish these solutions also in the archetypes and research communities.

Overall NFDI software architecture – data security and sovereignty

The NFDI4Ing technical Mission Statement was made available as an open document and as such is open for contributions and discussions under a preliminary URL ([link](#)). Based on the document we have put together

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some general technical recommendations that will guide the task area in their upcoming work:

- Use open specifications, where available, to ensure technical interoperability when establishing NFDI4Ing services.
- Define a common security and privacy framework and establish processes for NFDI4Ing services to ensure secure and trustworthy data exchange between all involved parties.
- Use an authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI) process for NFDI4Ing that is common across communities, easy to implement by resource providers and easy to understand by users, e.g. DFN-AAI.
- Create Service-Level Agreements for all NFDI4Ing resource providers that are easy to understand by users from different communities.
- Enable easy access to data sources available in different formats, either generic or community-based, to facilitate overcoming their heterogeneity and allow integrating data across communities, and to tools enabling the usage of the data.
- Make coarse-grained and fine-grained dataset (and other research object) search tools available. Consider a range of general-purpose and domain-specific/specialized search tools, exploiting general-purpose and domain-specific metadata.
- Create a clear NFDI4Ing persistent identifier (PID) policy, accommodating an appropriate PID usage, recognizing that established practices are at different levels of maturity for different resources and new PID types may emerge.

Based on the general recommendations the task area will work on more specific recommendations for tools that can be used to implement the recommendations within the services offered by NFDI4Ing. For that reason, the members of BASE SERVICES Measure *overall NFDI software architecture – data security and sovereignty* have been among the founding members of the “Task Force Tools for Authentication and Authorization Infrastructures” (TFT AAI) that aims to coordinate the efforts of all NFDI consortia towards a unified AAI. The task force was founded in parallel to the more general sections of the NFDI and will be transferred into a working group as part of the section “Common Infrastructures” early in 2022.

Community-based training on enabling data-driven science and FAIR data

During the first year of NFDI4Ing, in the BASE SERVICES Measure “Training and Education” we developed and adapted basic RDM training materials for engineers, currently in the format of self-guided trainings. These trainings were introduced to our community in our regular special interest group (SIG) meetings ([link](#)). Beyond this, the trainings are openly available in our “Education” repository ([link](#)). This repository has been chosen because it is ‘bi-directional’: The [community](#) can *receive* the trainings and can *give* feedback via issues. This enables a stronger community integration by contributing ideas, mentioning new topics and trends, and even pointing out ambiguities and mistakes in the trainings. Having the training materials published, we were readily contacted by the community on how to integrate RDM into university teaching.

Automated data and knowledge discovery in engineering literature

The aim of Task S-7-1 within our BASE SERVICES Measure *automated data and knowledge discovery in engineering literature* is to build and, within

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the framework of the legal possibilities, provide a corpus consisting of engineering research literature in a machine readable, uniformly structured format. As a starting point we identified literature that was rated as relevant by engineering researchers at the TU Darmstadt. Based on this literature list, we harvested exemplary articles of a journal via the publisher's API. Even in this rather small sample, not all articles contained the full text, but instead only the metadata. In addition to these initial technical tests, we started with the examination of the legal framework conditions in cooperation with Task S-7-2 (TIB Hannover). This was done by inspecting the text and data mining sections, if available, of existing license agreements between the University and State Library Darmstadt and the publishers as well as, also if available, the publishers' text and data mining policies. The results vary from publisher to publisher: Not all publishers provide information about whether text and data mining analyses of their content is allowed, some allow it under certain conditions and some demand consultation or separate license agreements. Inquiries have been made to several publishers regarding the provision of literature in machine-readable formats. Although up to now we are not yet able to provide structured literature for text and data mining, this preliminary work is a prerequisite for its legally compliant provision in the future.

COMMUNITY CLUSTERS (CCs)

This year's NFDI4Ing conference has been organized in a joined effort by *Measures activation and collaboration* (CC3, TU Braunschweig) and *participation* (CC4, TU Dresden). In accordance with the FAIR principles, the event was dedicated to *sharing* knowledge about RDM *Best-Practices*, *Research Software*, *Infrastructure and Cooperation*. In advance of the event we received close to 250 registrations for attending the two day

conference. In the end 130 participants on the first day and 115 on day two joined our event. In total, the conference program consisted of up to 4 tracks offering 8 workshops and 29 talks through all four mentioned topics. From a survey we have conducted after the conference, we know that 46% of the participants were especially interested in *Best-Practices* and 40% in the topic of *Research Software Engineering (RSE)*. The RSE-track was organized in cooperation with the German Society for Research Software and also attracted speakers and participants from the international community. Hence we made sure to provide at least one continuous English spoken track throughout the whole conference. Also part of the conference program was the election of the *NFDI4Ing Community Award 2021*. Participants was given the opportunity to elect their favorite RDM solutions from nine nominees. From the feedback that we got from the survey at the end of the conference, we considered that the conference was all in all a success. However, we learned that we could still improve. E.g. many people have not been aware of the fact that, although the conference being free of charge, they still needed to register in order to attend and receive the necessary login information. Also, attendees mentioned that the abstracts have been available on the website too late in advance of the actual conference. It would have been nice to record the sessions and to provide a possibility for the speakers to publish their work in conference proceedings could be taken into consideration to make the conferences contents available later on. With this in mind, we have published the "NFDI4Ing Conference 2021 - Collection of Abstracts" on Zenodo.

Another success was the announcement and the kick off meeting of the editorial board of the journal *ing.grid*. *ing.grid* will be an open access journal for FAIR data management in engineering sciences. Its editorial

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board currently consists of 22 members from all over the world. The first call for papers is planned for the second quarter of 2022.

Our community *Mechanical and Industrial Engineering* (DFG 41) has strengthened and linked networks within and beyond Germany. Therefore we are proud to announce the first DFG 41 Community Meeting at March 3rd 2022! Right now we are expanding our line-up for the event to further spread RDM into the community. Several national and international speakers will take part in this event. Further information will drop later this month, so stay tuned!

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